

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL SECTIONS 1–10

1. Pairwise phylogenetic controls for the simple morphometric comparisons

Flightless taxon	Closest volant relative(s) available for study
<i>Anas aucklandica</i>	<i>Anas chlorotis</i>
<i>Aptenodytes forsteri</i>	<i>Pelecanoides urinatrix</i> , <i>Oceanites oceanicus</i> , & <i>Diomedea immutabilis</i>
<i>Apteryx australis</i>	<i>Tinamus major saturatus</i>
<i>Aramidopsis plateni</i>	<i>Gallirallus striatus</i>
<i>Atlantisia rogersi</i>	<i>Porzana spiloptera</i>
<i>Casuarius unappendiculatus</i>	<i>Tinamus major saturatus</i>
<i>Dromaius novaehollandiae</i>	<i>Tinamus major saturatus</i>
<i>Dryolimnas cuvieri aldabranus</i>	<i>Dryolimnas cuvieri cuvieri</i>
<i>Eudiptes chrysocome crestatus</i>	<i>Pelecanoides urinatrix</i> , <i>Oceanites oceanicus</i> , & <i>Diomedea immutabilis</i>
<i>Fulica gigantea</i>	<i>Fulica armillata</i>
<i>Gallinula nesiotis</i>	<i>Gallinula chloropus chloropus</i>
<i>Gallirallus (=Tricholimnas) sylvestris</i>	<i>Ralls (=Gallirallus) philippensis philippensis</i>
<i>Gallirallus australis</i>	<i>Ralls (=Gallirallus) philippensis philippensis</i>
<i>Habroptila wallacii</i>	<i>Ralls (=Gallirallus) philippensis philippensis</i>
<i>Megacrex inepta</i>	<i>Himantornis haematopus</i>
<i>Mergus australis*</i>	<i>Mergus merganser americanus</i>
<i>Nesoclopeus woodfordi</i>	<i>Rallus (=Gallirallus) philippensis philippensis</i>
<i>Phalacrocorax harrisi</i>	<i>Phalacrocorax auritus</i>
<i>Pinguinus impennis</i>	<i>Alca torda</i>
<i>Podiceps taczanowskii</i>	<i>Podiceps occipitalis occipitalis</i>
<i>Podilymbus gigas</i>	<i>Podilymbus podiceps</i>
<i>Porzana palmeri</i>	<i>Porzana pusilla pusilla</i>
<i>Porzana sandwichensis</i>	<i>Porzana tabuensis tabuensis</i>
<i>Rhea americana intermedia</i>	<i>Tinamus major saturatus</i>
<i>Rollandia microptera</i>	<i>Rollandia rolland chilensis</i>
<i>Spheniscus demersus</i>	<i>Pelecanoides urinatrix</i> , <i>Oceanites oceanicus</i> , & <i>Diomedea immutabilis</i>
<i>Strigops habroptilus</i>	<i>Nestor notabilis</i>
<i>Struthio camelus</i>	<i>Tinamus major saturatus</i>
<i>Tachyeres ptereres</i>	<i>Tachyeres patachonicus</i>
<i>Tribonyx mortierii</i>	<i>Tribonyx ventralis whitei</i>
<i>Xenicus lyalli</i>	<i>Xenicus longipes</i>

Table S1. Pairwise phylogenetic comparisons for simple statistical analyses of morphometric shifts from volant to flightless or poor flighted taxa as sister taxon comparisons. Values of the three tubesnoses were averaged together. * indicates poor flying/‘incipiently flightless’.

2. *Apteryx australis* semi-alternating barb development pattern

2.1. *Apteryx australis* primary

Figure S1. *Apteryx australis* primary remex showing semi-alternating barb development pattern.

2.2. *Apteryx australis* tertial

Figure S2. *Apteryx australis* tertial showing semi-alternating barb development pattern.

2.3. *Apteryx australis* rectrix

Figure S3. *Apteryx australis* rectrix showing semi-alternating barb development pattern.

2.4. *Apteryx australis* dorsal contour

Figure S4. *Apteryx australis* dorsal contour showing semi-alternating barb development pattern.

3. Considerations of data acquisition

We attempted to account for challenges arising from the use of museum bird skins, which were often collected many years ago (especially true for extinct taxa) and therefore worn and degraded to some degree, as well as sewn together such that wings are almost always positioned tightly folded up against the body and rectrices are folded medially (hence why we examined the longest primary remex, the dorsal-most tertial remex, and the dorsal-most rectrix). This leads to problems of feather manipulation while obtaining data, especially when observing microscopic structures, and difficulty in controlling for homology between and within feathers.

As for homology, feather development occurring from the apex downward as the feather extends from the follicle (Ng & Li 2018) might suggest that homologous barbs are best described as those equally distant from the apex in terms of the number of barbs. However, differences in barb angle and density along the rachis can vary between the leading and trailing vanes, complicating this approach (e.g., the 10th barb from the apex on the leading vane with lower barb angle/density might be much further down the feather than the 10th barb from the apex on the trailing vane with higher barb angle/density). Furthermore, different feathers will not have the same length or total number of barbs (e.g., the 40th barb on remex of one species might not be in the same functional region of the feather as the 40th barb on the remex of another species). Additionally, counting barbs in such a manner is extremely time intensive, so an alternative view of homology might examine the entire feather from apex to calamus and describe the extent down the rachis as homologous (e.g., the barbs midway down the rachis are

homologous between feathers). However, without plucking the feathers from rare, strictly conserved museum skin specimens, this cannot be done with precision since the feather bases are inaccessible on the skins. These considerations of homology at the microscopic level do not even cover considerations between follicles across the body/plumage (e.g., differences in the number of primary remiges between species). Therefore, we chose to focus on the middle position along an exposed feather as a rough approximation of what might be considered a comparable intra-feather region/possible module across taxa, even if not precisely developmentally homologous.

As fractal structures, the largest and smallest order branches of feather filaments range from the macro- to microscopic, leading one to carefully consider measurement tools, especially the use of scaled microscopic images that are at risk of parallax errors when feathers are observed on three dimensional skins with extreme topography and challenges positioning the specimen into the perpendicular focal plane of the microscope. All these factors lead to noise in the data that we attempted to minimize through the use of the maneuverable microscope mounted stand, allowing for three dimensional skins to be observed with minimal parallax error, as well as our considerations of the subsequent statistical analyses (described in main text). Furthermore, different authors independently measured the same subset of the feathers in the dataset, finding reasonably consistent measurement values between researchers.

4. Repeated PCA under different initial conditions

	Only clades with flightless taxa		All clades	
	Long branches	No long branches	Long branches	No long branches
Whole plumage	84.17	85.98	84.69	86.53
Primaries	84.26	77.91	84.41	77.33
Tertials	86.44	86.62		
Rectrices	81.27	85.2		
Dorsal contours	78.75	79.47		
Ventral contours	82.37	84.37		

Table S2. Total proportion of the variation in the data explained by both PC1 and PC2. Bold values are those associated with PCA presented in the figures of the main text.

4.1. Whole plumage

4.1.1. Whole plumage: long branches, PCA of only clades with flightless taxa

PC1 and PC2 explain ~63.10% and ~21.07% of the variation, respectively.

Figure S5. PCA biplot of feathers from the whole plumage of only clades containing flightless taxa, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Red arrows indicate variable loadings. Leading and trailing barb lengths show similar loadings. N = 280 feathers, 56 taxa.

Figure S6. PCA of feathers from the whole plumage of only clades containing flightless taxa, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Green are volant taxa, red are flightless taxa, and yellow are poor flying/‘incipiently flightless’ taxa. N = 280 feathers, 56 taxa.

Figure S7. PCA of feathers from the whole plumage of only clades containing flightless taxa, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Color and shape indicate taxonomy as in Figure 2B. N = 280 feathers, 56 taxa.

Figure S8. PCA of feathers from the whole plumage of only clades containing flightless taxa, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Black are primaries, blue are tertials, green are rectrices, red are dorsal contours, and yellow are ventral contours. N = 280 feathers, 56 taxa.

All: Middle, Flightless Clades, Linear, w/ Long branches

Figure S9. PCA of feathers from the whole plumage of only clades containing flightless taxa, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Blue are semiaquatic, and orange are terrestrial. N = 280 feathers, 56 taxa.

4.1.2. Whole plumage: long branches, PCA of all clades (see Fig. 2)

PC1 and PC2 explain ~63.63% and ~21.06% of the variation, respectively.

Figure S10. PCA biplot of feathers from the whole plumage of all clades, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Red arrows indicate variable loadings. Leading and trailing barb lengths show similar loadings. N = 307 feathers, 83 taxa.

4.1.3. Whole plumage: no long branches (i.e., without Palaeognathae, Sphenisciformes, and Procellariiformes), PCA of only clades with flightless taxa

PC1 and PC2 explain ~66.53% and ~19.45% of the variation, respectively.

Figure S11. PCA biplot of feathers from the whole plumage of only clades containing flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Red arrows indicate variable loadings. Leading and trailing barb lengths show similar loadings. N = 220 feathers, 44 taxa.

All: Middle, Flightless clades, Linear, w/o Long branches

Figure S12. PCA of feathers from the whole plumage of only clades containing flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Green are volant taxa, red are flightless taxa, and yellow are poor flying/‘incipiently flightless’ taxa. N = 220 feathers, 44 taxa.

Figure S13. PCA of feathers from the whole plumage of only clades containing flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Color indicates clade as in Figure 2B. N = 220 feathers, 44 taxa.

Figure S14. PCA of feathers from the whole plumage of only clades containing flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Black are primaries, blue are tertials, green are rectrices, red are dorsal contours, and yellow are ventral contours. N = 220 feathers, 44 taxa.

All: Middle, Flightless clades, Linear, w/o Long branches

Figure S15. PCA of feathers from the whole plumage of only clades containing flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Blue are semiaquatic, and orange are terrestrial. N = 220 feathers, 44 taxa.

4.1.4. Whole plumage: no long branches (i.e., without Palaeognathae, Sphenisciformes, and Procellariiformes), PCA of all clades

PC1 and PC2 explain ~65.96% and ~20.57% of the variation, respectively.

Figure S16. PCA biplot of feathers from the whole plumage of all clades, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Red arrows indicate variable loadings. Leading and trailing barb lengths show similar loadings. N = 267 feathers, 75 taxa.

Figure S17. PCA biplot of feathers from the whole plumage of all clades, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Green are volant taxa, red are flightless taxa, and yellow are poor flying/‘incipiently flightless’ taxa. N = 267 feathers, 75 taxa.

Figure S18. PCA biplot of feathers from the whole plumage of all clades, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Color indicates clade as in Figure 2B. N = 267 feathers, 75 taxa.

All: Middle, Total, Linear, w/o Long branches

Figure S19. PCA biplot of feathers from the whole plumage of all clades, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Black are primaries, blue are tertials, green are rectrices, red are dorsal contours, and yellow are ventral contours. N = 267 feathers, 75 taxa.

All: Middle, Total, Linear, w/o Long branches

Figure S20. PCA biplot of feathers from the whole plumage of all clades, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Blue are semiaquatic, and orange are terrestrial. N = 267 feathers, 75 taxa.

4.2. Primaries

As a result of not log-transforming the data, bear in mind that for the shifts in metrics from a volant ancestor (i.e., the origin on the plots of $\Delta PC1$ and $\Delta PC2$), extreme values are not consistently scaled after dividing the

metric by the rachis length at that middle barb pair. The same holds true for the feather types other than primaries (sections 3.3–3.7).

4.2.1. Primary: long branches, PC space established by only clades with flightless taxa

PC1 and PC2 explain ~64.55% and ~19.71% of the variation, respectively.

Figure S21. PCA biplot of primaries of only clades containing flightless taxa, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Red arrows indicate variable loadings. N = 56 taxa.

Primary: Middle, Flightless clades, Linear, w/ Long branches

Figure S22. PCA of primaries of only clades containing flightless taxa, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Green are volant taxa, red are flightless taxa, and yellow are poor flying/‘incipiently flightless’ taxa. N = 56 taxa.

Figure S23. Simple pairwise phylogenetic PCA shift of primaries during flight loss based on an initial morphospace of only clades containing flightless taxa, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Color and shape indicate taxonomy as in Figure 3. Open circle is poor flyer/‘incipiently flightless’. N = 31 taxa.

Figure S24. Simple pairwise phylogenetic PCA shift of primaries during flight loss based on an initial morphospace of only clades containing flightless taxa, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Blue are semiaquatic, and orange are terrestrial. Open circle is poor flyer/‘incipiently flightless’. N = 31 taxa.

4.2.2. Primary: long branches, PC space established by all clades

PC1 and PC2 explain ~65.30% and ~19.11% of the variation, respectively.

Figure S25. PCA biplot of primaries of all clades, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Red arrows indicate variable loadings. Barb width and barbule length show similar loadings. N = 83 taxa.

Figure S26. PCA of primaries of all clades, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Green are volant taxa, red are flightless taxa, yellow are poor flying/‘incipiently flightless’ taxa, and black are taxa of unknown flight capability. N = 83 taxa.

Figure S27. Simple pairwise phylogenetic PCA shift of primaries during flight loss based on an initial morphospace of all clades, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Color and shape indicate taxonomy as in Figure 3. Open circle is poor flyer/‘incipiently flightless’. N = 31 taxa

Figure S28. Simple pairwise phylogenetic PCA shift of primaries during flight loss based on an initial morphospace of all clades, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Blue are semiaquatic, and orange are terrestrial. Open circle is poor flyer/‘incipiently flightless’. N = 31 taxa.

4.2.3. Primary: no long branches (i.e., without Palaeognathae, Sphenisciformes, and Procellariiformes), PC space established by only clades with flightless taxa

PC1 and PC2 explain ~58.85% and ~19.06% of the variation, respectively.

Figure S29. PCA biplot of primaries of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Red arrows indicate variable loadings. Leading and trailing barb lengths have similar loadings. N = 44 taxa.

Figure S30. PCA of primaries of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Green are volant taxa, red are flightless taxa, and yellow are poor flying/‘incipiently flightless’ taxa. N = 44 taxa.

Figure S31. Simple pairwise phylogenetic PCA shift of primaries during flight loss based on an initial morphospace of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Color indicates clade as in Figure 3. Open circle is poor flyer/‘incipiently flightless’. N = 23 taxa.

Figure S32. Simple pairwise phylogenetic PCA shift of primaries during flight loss based on an initial morphospace of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Blue are semiaquatic, and orange are terrestrial. Open circle is poor flyer/‘incipiently flightless’. N = 23 taxa.

4.2.4. Primary: no long branches (i.e., without Palaeognathae, Sphenisciformes, and Procellariiformes), PC space established by all clades

PC1 and PC2 explain ~55.51% and ~21.82% of the variation, respectively.

Figure S33. PCA biplot of primaries of all clades, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Red arrows indicate variable loadings. N = 75 taxa.

Figure S34. PCA of primaries of all clades, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Green are volant taxa, red are flightless taxa, yellow are poor flying/‘incipiently flightless’ taxa, and black are taxa of unknown flight capability. N = 75 taxa.

Figure S35. Simple pairwise phylogenetic PCA shift of primaries during flight loss based on an initial morphospace of all clades, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Color indicates clade as in Figure 3. Open circle is poor flyer/‘incipiently flightless’. N = 23 taxa.

Figure S36. Simple pairwise phylogenetic PCA shift of primaries during flight loss based on an initial morphospace of all clades, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Blue are semiaquatic, and orange are terrestrial. Open circle is poor flyer/‘incipiently flightless’. N = 23 taxa.

4.3. Tertials

4.3.1. Tertial: long branches, PC space established by only clades with flightless taxa

PC1 and PC2 explain ~58.39% and ~28.05% of the variation, respectively.

Figure S37. PCA biplot of tertials of only clades with flightless taxa, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Red arrows indicate variable loadings. N = 56 taxa.

Tertial: Middle, Flightless clades, Linear, w/ Long branches

Figure S38. PCA of tertials of only clades with flightless taxa, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Green are volant taxa, red are flightless taxa, and yellow are poor flying/‘incipiently flightless’ taxa. N = 56 taxa.

4.3.2. Tertial: no long branches (i.e., without Palaeognathae, Sphenisciformes, and Procellariiformes), PC space established by only clades with flightless taxa

PC1 and PC2 explain ~65.82% and ~20.80% of the variation, respectively.

Figure S39. PCA biplot of tertials of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Red arrows indicate variable loadings. Leading and trailing barb lengths have similar loadings. Barbule length and barb width have similar loadings. N = 44 taxa.

Figure S40. PCA of tertials of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Green are volant taxa, red are flightless taxa, and yellow are poor flying/‘incipiently flightless’ taxa. N = 44 taxa.

Figure S41. Simple pairwise phylogenetic PCA shift of tertials during flight loss based on an initial morphospace of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Color indicates clade as in Figure 3. Open circle is poor flyer/‘incipiently flightless’. N = 23 taxa.

Tertial: Middle, Flightless clades, Linear, w/o Long branches

Figure S42. Simple pairwise phylogenetic PCA shift of tertials during flight loss based on an initial morphospace of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Blue are semiaquatic, and orange are terrestrial. Open circle is poor flyer/'incipiently flightless'. N = 23 taxa.

4.4. Rectrices

4.4.1. Rectrix: long branches, PC space established by only clades with flightless taxa

PC1 and PC2 explain ~58.66% and ~22.61% of the variation, respectively.

Figure S43. PCA biplot of rectrices of only clades with flightless taxa, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Red arrows indicate variable loadings. N = 56 taxa.

Figure S44. PCA of rectrices of only clades with flightless taxa, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Green are volant taxa, red are flightless taxa, and yellow are poor flying/'incipiently flightless' taxa. N = 56 taxa.

4.4.2. Retrix: no long branches (i.e., without Palaeognathae, Sphenisciformes, and Procellariiformes), PC space established by only clades with flightless taxa

PC1 and PC2 explain ~67.20% and ~18.00% of the variation, respectively.

Figure S45. PCA biplot of rectrices of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Red arrows indicate variable loadings. N = 44 taxa.

Figure S46. PCA of rectrices of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Green are volant taxa, red are flightless taxa, and yellow are poor flying/‘incipiently flightless’ taxa. N = 44 taxa.

Retrix: Middle, Flightless clades, Linear, w/o Long branches

Figure S47. Simple pairwise phylogenetic PCA shift of rectrices during flight loss based on an initial morphospace of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Color indicates clade as in Figure 3. Open circle is poor flyer/‘incipiently flightless’. N = 23 taxa.

Retrix: Middle, Flightless clades, Linear, w/o Long branches

Figure S48. Simple pairwise phylogenetic PCA shift of rectrices during flight loss based on an initial morphospace of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Blue are semiaquatic, and orange are terrestrial. Open circle is poor flyer/‘incipiently flightless’. N = 23 taxa.

4.5. Dorsal contours

4.5.1. Dorsal contour: long branches, PC space established by only clades with flightless taxa

PC1 and PC2 explain ~56.80% and ~21.95% of the variation, respectively.

Figure S49. PCA biplot of dorsal contours of only clades with flightless taxa, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Red arrows indicate variable loadings. N = 56 taxa.

Figure S50. PCA of dorsal contours of only clades with flightless taxa, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Green are volant taxa, red are flightless taxa, and yellow are poor flying/‘incipiently flightless’ taxa. N = 56 taxa.

4.5.2. Dorsal contour: no long branches (i.e., without Palaeognathae, Sphenisciformes, and Procellariiformes), PC space established by only clades with flightless taxa

PC1 and PC2 explain ~57.67% and ~21.80% of the variation, respectively.

Figure S51. PCA biplot of dorsal contours of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Red arrows indicate variable loadings. N = 44 taxa.

Dorsal.Contour: Middle, Flightless clades, Linear, w/o Long branches

Figure S52. PCA of dorsal contours of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Green are volant taxa, red are flightless taxa, and yellow are poor flying/‘incipiently flightless’ taxa. N = 44 taxa.

Dorsal.Contour: Middle, Flightless clades, Linear, w/o Long branches

Figure S53. Simple pairwise phylogenetic PCA shift of dorsal contours during flight loss based on an initial morphospace of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Color indicates clade as in Figure 3. Open circle is poor flyer/‘incipiently flightless’. N = 23 taxa

Dorsal.Contour: Middle, Flightless clades, Linear, w/o Long branches

Figure S54. Simple pairwise phylogenetic PCA shift of dorsal contours during flight loss based on an initial morphospace of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Blue are semiaquatic, and orange are terrestrial. Open circle is poor flyer/'incipiently flightless'. N = 23 taxa.

4.6. Ventral contours

4.6.1. Ventral contour: long branches, PC space established by only clades with flightless taxa

PC1 and PC2 explain ~66.12% and ~16.25% of the variation, respectively.

Figure S55. PCA biplot of ventral contours of only clades with flightless taxa, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Red arrows indicate variable loadings. N = 56 taxa.

Figure S56. PCA of ventral contours of only clades with flightless taxa, with penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous included. Green are volant taxa, red are flightless taxa, and yellow are poor flying/‘incipiently flightless’ taxa. N = 56 taxa.

4.6.2. Ventral contour: no long branches (i.e., without Palaeognathae, Sphenisciformes, and Procellariiformes), PC space established by only clades with flightless taxa

PC1 and PC2 explain ~70.77% and ~13.60% of the variation, respectively.

Figure S57. PCA biplot of ventral contours of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Red arrows indicate variable loadings. N = 44 taxa.

Figure S58. PCA of ventral contours of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Green are volant taxa, red are flightless taxa, and yellow are poor flying/‘incipiently flightless’ taxa. N = 44 taxa.

Figure S59. Simple pairwise phylogenetic PCA shift of ventral contours during flight loss based on an initial morphospace of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Color indicates clade as in Figure 3. Open circle is poor flyer/‘incipiently flightless’. N = 23 taxa.

Figure S60. Simple pairwise phylogenetic PCA shift of ventral contours during flight loss based on an initial morphospace of only clades with flightless taxa, except penguins/tubenoses and ratites/tinamous. Blue are semiaquatic, and orange are terrestrial. Open circle is poor flyer/‘incipiently flightless’. N = 23 taxa.

4.7. Summary plots of simple, pairwise phylogenetically controlled PCA

We ran PCA to establish a morphospace and then added phylogenetic control, such that the shift in PC values can be observed between flightless taxa and their closest volant relative(s), with the origin of the ΔPC plots representing the volant relative(s) (i.e., a hypothetical ancestral state). In combination with the above whole plumage PCA without phylogenetic control, we see that 1) flightless taxa tend to show greater feather morphological diversity than do volant taxa prior to phylogenetic control and 2) barb width tends to intermediately correlate between the filament length metrics and rachis width or that barb width correlates with barbule length (Fig. 2; Figs. S61–S62).

When examining the primaries, upon loss of flight (or incipient loss of flight), there appears to be an initial increase in filament lengths from their volant relatives. Terrestrial flightless taxa, especially some rails, tend to have greater shifts toward longer barbs from their volant relatives than do semiaquatic flightless taxa among more recently flightless clades. Feather types in ratites other than primaries tend to shift toward filament length reduction, rather than the more diverse changes seen in their primaries. Semiaquatic flightless taxa tend to shift their primaries more towards wider filaments and longer barbules from their volant relatives than do terrestrial flightless taxa among more recently flightless clades.

These patterns appear to be strongest in primaries, followed by the rectrix, tertial, dorsal contour, and ventral contour. In other words, clade and ecological categories begin to center around the ΔPC plot origin and the difference between flightless and volant taxa feather morphological diversity prior to phylogenetic control seems to decrease when simple phylogenetic control is added. Our results are generally supported when repeating the PCA under varying initial conditions (i.e., with and without ‘long branch’ clades where flightlessness occurred 10’s of millions of years ago, as well as with and without clades that don’t include flightless taxa in the case of the primaries).

Figure S61. Phylogenetically controlled shifts in feather morphospace of flightless and ‘incipiently flightless’ taxa from their closest volant relative(s) in, A, primaries, B, rectrices, C, tertials, D, dorsal contours, and, E,

ventral contours according to clade. Initial PCA morphospace prior to phylogenetic control established using only clades with flightless taxa for all panels. Insets show the loading plots for the five linear metrics on the PC1 and PC2. Each of the five metrics is divided by the length of the rachis from the apical-most node to the middle barb pair measured here. Ratite point shape indicates genus (bearing in mind that the semi-alternating barb development pattern in *Apteryx* could shift its position either towards longer filament ratites like *Struthio* and *Dromaius* or towards shorter filament ratites like *Rhea* and *Casuaris*, if using the example of the primary). *The red open circle of the Anseriformes represents the poor-flying/‘incipiently flightless’ *Mergus australis*. N = 30 flightless and 1 ‘incipiently flightless’ taxa (initial morphospace established by 56 taxa).

Figure S62. Phylogenetically controlled shifts in feather morphospace of flightless and ‘incipiently flightless’ taxa from their closest volant relative(s) in, A, primaries, B, rectrices, C, tertials, D, dorsal contours, and, E, ventral contours according to ecology. Initial PCA morphospace prior to phylogenetic control established using only clades with flightless taxa for all panels. Insets show the loading plots for the five linear metrics on the PC1 and PC2. Each of the five metrics is divided by the length of the rachis from the apical-most node to the middle barb pair measured here. *The blue open circle of the semiaquatic taxa represents the poor-flying/‘incipiently flightless’ *Mergus australis*. N = 30 flightless and 1 ‘incipiently flightless’ taxa (initial morphospace established by 56 taxa).

When simple phylogenetic controls are introduced and the shift from volant relative(s) to flightless taxa in the morphospaces are observed, the most prevalent patterns according to clade and ecology seem to occur in the primaries. This is consistent with the primary’s crucial role in flight, as well as its occasional use in swimming in some taxa. As observed in the primaries, there appears to possibly be an initial increase in filament lengths

upon the loss of flight, possibly indicating less robust feathers that are under less selective pressure for use in flight and perhaps for increased thermoregulation.

Overall, semiaquatic flightless taxa tend to have shifts directed towards wider filaments and longer barbules compared to the terrestrial flightless taxa, hypothetically consistent with locomotion through a dense water medium.

Among taxa that lost flight relatively recently, terrestrial flightless taxa tend to shift towards longer filaments than semiaquatic flightless taxa.

5. Asymmetry: middle & basal regions (see Fig. 3)

5.1. Tertial asymmetry, middle & basal regions

Figure S63. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in barb asymmetry values due to flight loss of tertials (middle & basal region combined) according to clade. N = 60 barb pairs (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

Figure S64. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in barb asymmetry values due to flight loss of tertials (middle & basal region combined) according to swim score. Blue are semiaquatic, and orange are terrestrial. N = 60 barb pairs (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

5.2. Rectrix asymmetry, middle & basal regions

Figure S65. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in barb asymmetry values due to flight loss of rectrices (middle & basal region combined) according to clade. N = 60 barb pairs (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

Figure S66. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in barb asymmetry values due to flight loss of rectrices (middle & basal region combined) according to swim score. Blue are semiaquatic, and orange are terrestrial. N = 60 barb pairs (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

5.3. Dorsal contour asymmetry, middle & basal regions

Figure S67. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in barb asymmetry values due to flight loss of dorsal contours (middle & basal region combined) according to clade. N = 60 barb pairs (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

Figure S68. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in barb asymmetry values due to flight loss of dorsal contours (middle & basal region combined) according to swim score. Blue are semiaquatic, and orange are terrestrial. N = 60 barb pairs (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

5.4. Ventral contour asymmetry, middle & basal regions

Figure S69. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in barb asymmetry values due to flight loss of ventral contours (middle & basal region combined) according to clade. N = 60 barb pairs (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

Figure S70. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in barb asymmetry values due to flight loss of ventral contours (middle & basal region combined) according to swim score. Blue are semiaquatic, and orange are terrestrial. N = 60 barb pairs (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

6. Filament densities: leading/trailing barbs, distal/proximal barbules, middle & basal regions (see Fig. 4)

6.1. Terial densities, leading/trailing barbs, distal/proximal barbules, middle & basal regions

Figure S71. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in leading barb densities due to flight loss of tertials (middle & basal region combined) according to clade. N = 60 leading barb density measurements (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

Figure S72. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in trailing barb densities due to flight loss of tertials (middle & basal region combined) according to clade. N = 60 trailing barb density measurements (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

Figure S73. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in trailing barbule densities (distal & proximal combined) due to flight loss of tertials (middle & basal region combined) according to clade. N = 120 barbule density measurements (distal & proximal), 60 trailing barbs (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

6.2. Rectrix densities, leading/trailing barbs, distal/proximal barbules, middle & basal regions

Figure S74. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in leading barb densities due to flight loss of rectrices (middle & basal region combined) according to clade. N = 60 leading barb density measurements (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

Figure S75. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in trailing barb densities due to flight loss of rectrices (middle & basal region combined) according to clade. N = 60 trailing barb density measurements (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

Figure S76. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in trailing barbule densities (distal & proximal combined) due to flight loss of rectrices (middle & basal region combined) according to clade. N = 120 barbule density measurements (distal & proximal), 60 trailing barbs (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

6.3. Dorsal contour densities, leading/trailing barbs, distal/proximal barbules, middle & basal regions

Figure S77. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in leading barb densities due to flight loss of dorsal contours (middle & basal region combined) according to clade. N = 60 leading barb density measurements (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

Figure S78. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in trailing barb densities due to flight loss of dorsal contours (middle & basal region combined) according to clade. N = 60 trailing barb density measurements (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

Figure S79. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in trailing barbule densities (distal & proximal combined) due to flight loss of dorsal contours (middle & basal region combined) according to clade. N = 120 barbule density measurements (distal & proximal), 60 trailing barbs (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

6.4. Ventral contour densities, leading/trailing barbs, distal/proximal barbules, middle & basal regions

Figure S80. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in leading barb densities due to flight loss of ventral contours (middle & basal region combined) according to clade. N = 60 leading barb density measurements (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

Figure S81. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in trailing barb densities due to flight loss of ventral contours (middle & basal region combined) according to clade. N = 60 trailing barb density measurements (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

Figure S82. Pairwise phylogenetic shifts in trailing barbule densities (distal & proximal combined) due to flight loss of ventral contours (middle & basal region combined) according to clade. N = 120 barbule density measurements (distal & proximal), 60 trailing barbs (middle & basal region), 30 taxa.

7. Simple, phylogenetic pairwise regressions on macro- and microscopic traits

We report simplistic regression analyses to examine morphological divergence (Δ) versus maximum estimated time of flightlessness (based mostly on phylogenetic divergence ages from published molecular studies with dated nodes, but also informed by time of geographic isolation) between the phylogenetically controlled volant-flightless sister pairs. More specifically, the shift (Δ) is the morphometric variable from the phylogenetically closest volant taxa to the flightless taxon, and it is examined against divergence age. These

helped us establish hypotheses for morphological changes potentially linked to flight loss that can then be more rigorously tested through more sophisticated phylogenetic comparative methods.

We lacked known age estimates for *Gallinula nesiotis* and *Podilymbus gigas*, the latter is simply estimated to be less than 960 Ka. We can \log_{10} -transform before the linear model is applied in order to examine the intercept, slope, and R^2 , but some ratites return ‘inf. error’ in R when filaments are absent (i.e., you cannot take the log of zero). Finally, we compared macroscopic whole body changes to microscopic changes in the primaries.

7.1. Macroscopic traits: pairwise regressions

7.1.1. Body mass vs. divergence age

Figure S83. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed body mass (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age. $\Delta = \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Mass}_F) - \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Mass}_V)$. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown.

Figure S84. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed body mass (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age with penguins and ratites removed. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown.

7.1.2. Wing length (scaled to body mass) vs. divergence age

Figure S85. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed wing length/body mass (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age. $\Delta = \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Wing}_F/\text{Mass}_F) - \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Wing}_V/\text{Mass}_V)$. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown.

Figure S86. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed wing length/body mass (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age with penguins and ratites removed. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown.

7.1.3. Tail length (scaled to body mass) vs. divergence age

Figure S87. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed tail fan length/body mass (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age. $\Delta = \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Tail}_F/\text{Mass}_F) - \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Tail}_V/\text{Mass}_V)$. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown.

Figure S88. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed tail fan length/body mass (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age with penguins and ratites removed. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown.

7.1.4. Difference in wing and tail length vs. divergence age

Figure S89. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed wing length minus tail fan length (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age. $\Delta = (\text{Log}_{10}(\text{Wing}_F) - \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Tail}_F)) - (\text{Log}_{10}(\text{Wing}_V) - \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Tail}_V))$. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown.

Figure S90. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed wing length minus tail fan length (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age with penguins and ratites removed. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown.

7.1.5. Difference in wing and tarsus length vs. divergence age

Figure S91. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed wing length minus tarsus length (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age. $\Delta = (\text{Log}_{10}(\text{Wing}_F) - \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Tarsus}_F)) - (\text{Log}_{10}(\text{Wing}_V) - \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Tarsus}_V))$. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown.

Figure S92. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed wing length minus tarsus length (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age with penguins and ratites removed. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown.

7.1.6. Macroscopic trait pairwise regression summary

The best signatures of flightlessness based on these regressions with simplistic phylogenetic control (above) are body mass increase, wing length/mass ratio decrease, and tail fan length/mass ratio decrease. This may be consistent even in early evolution, according to these results.

The shifts might appear to be more rapid in semiaquatic taxa in these results due to either water buoyancy that more readily allows for larger body size or novel selective pressures related to locomotion in water (rather than simply a relaxation of selection for flight).

7.2. Microscopic traits: pairwise regressions

Primary remiges were examined under the assumption that they are likely to show the most prominent signal to noise ratio, because they are most crucial for flight among our sampled feather positions. The middle region exposed on the rachis was examined for barb (leading and trailing) lengths, rachis width, and (distal) barbule length, all of which were scaled to rachis length. Log₁₀-transformation was used to determine the shift from volant to flightless phylogenetically related taxa as follows: $\Delta = \text{Log}_{10}(M_F/L_F) - \text{Log}_{10}(M_V/L_V)$, where M_F and M_V are the microscopic morphometric and L_F and L_V are the rachis length from the apical/distal node of the feather to that point of the middle region exposed along the feather, for flightless and volant sister taxa respectively. Barb width was not examined since it correlates with other variables (e.g., barbule length) and pushes the limits of the microscope's measurement capability.

7.2.1. Rachis width vs. divergence age

Figure S93. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed rachis width/rachis length (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age. $\Delta = \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Width}_F/\text{Length}_F) - \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Width}_V/\text{Length}_V)$. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown.

Figure S94. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed rachis width/rachis length (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age with penguins and ratites removed. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown.

Figure S95. Boxplots of shift in \log_{10} -transformed rachis width/rachis length (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age with penguins and ratites removed. T: Terrestrial taxa. A: Semiaquatic taxa. Not shown to scale.

7.2.2. Leading barb length vs. divergence age

Figure S96. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed leading barb length/rachis length (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age. $\Delta = \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Barb}_F/\text{Rachis}_F) - \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Barb}_V/\text{Rachis}_V)$. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown. Vertical dashed line indicates cassowary divergence age since barb loss precludes \log_{10} -transformation and inclusion in the plot/regressions.

Figure S97. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed leading barb length/rachis length (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age with penguins and ratites removed. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown.

7.2.3. Trailing barb length vs. divergence age

Figure S98. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed trailing barb length/rachis length (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age. $\Delta = \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Barb}_F/\text{Rachis}_F) - \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Barb}_V/\text{Rachis}_V)$. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown. Vertical dashed line indicates cassowary divergence age since barb loss precludes \log_{10} -transformation and inclusion in the plot/regressions.

Figure S99. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed trailing barb length/rachis length (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age with penguins and ratites removed. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown.

7.2.4. Barbule length vs. divergence age

Figure S100. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed distal barbule length/rachis length (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age. $\Delta = \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Barbule}_F/\text{Rachis}_F) - \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Barbule}_V/\text{Rachis}_V)$. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown. Vertical dashed lines indicate emu and cassowary (left) and rhea (right) divergence ages since barbules loss precludes \log_{10} -transformation and inclusion in the plot/regressions.

Figure S101. Shift in \log_{10} -transformed distal barbule length/rachis length (flightless minus volant sister taxon comparisons) versus divergence age with penguins and ratites removed. Top: clade colors as in plots above. Bottom: blue points are semiaquatic, while black are terrestrial. Linear regression results shown.

7.2.5. Microscopic trait pairwise regression summary

Rachis width generally shifts negatively from the volant ancestor – notably decreasing in terrestrial taxa, although there is a less negative shift in semiaquatic taxa. The reversed correlations seen without the ‘long branches’ of ratites and penguins are likely flukes of low sample size, since the data points representing recently diverging semiaquatic flightless taxa are more positive than terrestrial flightless taxa of similar age. This possibly shows that the pattern in rachis width upon flight loss is more apparent after long divergence times and specialized adaptation to non-flight.

Barb length increases with flightlessness generally, more so in the leading than the trailing vane because of high vane asymmetry in volant ancestors. Early evolution may show more rapid barb length increase in terrestrial flightless taxa than in semiaquatic flightless taxa. Late evolution may show a reversal of this trend – ratites eventually lose barbs, while penguins have long barbs relative to their rachis length.

Barbule length tends to increase with flightlessness, but this trend is likely not as prevalent as in barb lengths. There may be a strong shift in semiaquatic flightless taxa, even in early in their evolution. The ratite pattern is diverse – if they retain barbules, the barbules tend to be long; otherwise, barbules are lost entirely.

7.3. Comparison of pairwise regression slopes and R²

7.3.1. Absolute value of the regression slope

Metric	Bin	Absolute value of slope, Long branches
Mass	Terr.	0.4676
Tail	Aqua.	0.466
Wing	Aqua.	0.4426
Mass	All	0.42401
Wing	All	0.39271
Mass	Aqua.	0.3894
Wing	Terr.	0.3862
Tail	All	0.34156
Tail	Terr.	0.27458
Barbule	Aqua.	0.24759
Barb L	Aqua.	0.1656
Barbule	All	0.15651
Rachis W	Terr.	0.08879
Barbule	Terr.	0.08139
Barb T	Aqua.	0.07647
Barb T	Terr.	0.05933
Barb L	All	0.05154
Barb L	Terr.	0.03776
Rachis W	Aqua.	0.019878
Rachis W	All	0.007466
Barb T	All	0.003552

Table S3. Absolute value of regression slopes with penguins and ratites included for macroscopic (blue) and microscopic (red) traits.

Metric	Bin	Absolute value of slope, No long branches
Tail	Aqua.	0.2192
Wing	Aqua.	0.1809
Barbule	Aqua.	0.1773
Mass	Aqua.	0.1725

Mass	Terr.	0.1619
Mass	All	0.14984
Tail	All	0.1457
Wing	All	0.11637
Tail	Terr.	0.10719
Barbule	All	0.10668
Wing	Terr.	0.106
Barb L	Terr.	0.07536
Barb L	All	0.07242
Rachis W	Terr.	0.07118
Barb T	Terr.	0.02558
Rachis W	Aqua.	0.02464
Rachis W	All	0.02243
Barb T	All	0.01887
Barb L	Aqua.	0.01848
Barbule	Terr.	0.008205
Barb T	Aqua.	0.002853

Table S4. Absolute value of regression slopes with penguins and ratites removed for macroscopic (blue) and microscopic (red) traits.

7.3.2. R² value of the regression

Metric	Bin	R², Long branches
Barbule	Aqua.	0.7254
Tail	Aqua.	0.6859
Wing	Aqua.	0.6617
Mass	Aqua.	0.6061
Barb L	Aqua.	0.5627
Wing	All	0.5024
Tail	All	0.4934
Mass	All	0.4804
Wing	Terr.	0.4651
Mass	Terr.	0.4524
Tail	Terr.	0.4205
Barb T	Aqua.	0.4057
Rachis W	Aqua.	0.3192
Barbule	All	0.2193
Rachis W	Terr.	0.08588
Barb T	Terr.	0.08576
Barbule	Terr.	0.07525
Barb L	All	0.05528
Barb L	Terr.	0.02939
Barb T	All	0.0004124

Rachis W	All	0.000405
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Table S5. R² of regressions with penguins and ratites included for macroscopic (blue) and microscopic (red) traits.

Metric	Bin	Adjusted R ² , Long branches
Barbule	Aqua.	0.6949
Tail	Aqua.	0.651
Wing	Aqua.	0.6242
Mass	Aqua.	0.5624
Barb L	Aqua.	0.5141
Wing	All	0.4833
Tail	All	0.4739
Mass	All	0.4604
Wing	Terr.	0.4295
Mass	Terr.	0.4159
Tail	Terr.	0.3818
Barb T	Aqua.	0.3397
Rachis W	Aqua.	0.2436
Barbule	All	0.1853
Rachis W	Terr.	0.02494
Barb T	Terr.	0.02046
Barb L	All	0.01749
Barbule	Terr.	-0.00181
Rachis W	All	-0.03804
Barb T	All	-0.03957
Barb L	Terr.	-0.03994

Table S6. Adjusted R² of regressions with penguins and ratites included for macroscopic (blue) and microscopic (red) traits.

Metric	Bin	R ² , No long branches
Barbule	Aqua.	0.4404
Tail	Aqua.	0.4118
Rachis W	Aqua.	0.3069
Wing	Aqua.	0.3028
Mass	Aqua.	0.281
Tail	All	0.2207
Mass	Terr.	0.1973
Mass	All	0.188
Barb L	All	0.157
Barb L	Terr.	0.1563
Wing	All	0.1526
Wing	Terr.	0.1489
Tail	Terr.	0.1279
Barb L	Aqua.	0.123

Rachis W	Terr.	0.0788
Barb T	Terr.	0.05029
Rachis W	All	0.0381
Barb T	All	0.03567
Barbule	All	0.01229
Barb T	Aqua.	0.001714
Barbule	Terr.	0.0007738

Table S7. R² of regressions with penguins and ratites removed for macroscopic (blue) and microscopic (red) traits.

Metric	Bin	Adjusted R², No long branches
Barbule	Aqua.	0.3471
Tail	Aqua.	0.3138
Rachis W	Aqua.	0.1914
Wing	Aqua.	0.1866
Tail	All	0.1774
Mass	Aqua.	0.1612
Mass	All	0.1429
Mass	Terr.	0.117
Barb L	All	0.1102
Wing	All	0.1055
Barb L	Terr.	0.07188
Wing	Terr.	0.0638
Tail	Terr.	0.04064
Rachis W	Terr.	-0.01332
Rachis W	All	-0.01534
Barb T	All	-0.0179
Barb L	Aqua.	-0.02312
Barbule	All	-0.04258
Barb T	Terr.	-0.04468
Barbule	Terr.	-0.09915
Barb T	Aqua.	-0.1647

Table S8. Adjusted R² of regressions with penguins and ratites removed for macroscopic (blue) and microscopic (red) traits.

7.3.3. Regression parameters summary

Typically, macroscopic anatomical shifts seem to occur earlier and are stronger indicators of flightlessness than microscopic anatomical shifts. However, barbule length and rachis width in semiaquatic taxa, and to a lesser extent barb length in terrestrial taxa, might change soon after flight loss when examined with regression under simple phylogenetic control.

8. Scaling barb & barbule densities to rachis width

The issue of scaling confounds in density values for barbs and barbules can be partly addressed by multiplying the density values by rachis width at that feather position. The results support much of our interpretations from unscaled density values.

Figure S102. Shifts in flightless taxa from their closest volant relative(s) in leading barb densities on the combined middle and basal regions of primaries, scaled by rachis width and grouped by clade.

Figure S103. Shifts in flightless taxa from their closest volant relative(s) in trailing barb densities on the combined middle and basal regions of primaries, scaled by rachis width and grouped by clade.

Figure S104. Shifts in flightless taxa from their closest volant relative(s) in combined distal and proximal barbule densities on the combined middle and basal regions of primaries, scaled by rachis width and grouped by clade.

Figure S105. Shifts in flightless taxa from their closest volant relative(s) in leading barb densities on the combined middle and basal regions of primaries, scaled by rachis width. All clades are plotted.

Figure S106. Shifts in flightless taxa from their closest volant relative(s) in trailing barb densities on the combined middle and basal regions of primaries, scaled by rachis width. All clades are plotted.

Figure S107. Shifts in flightless taxa from their closest volant relative(s) in combined distal and proximal barbule densities on the combined middle and basal regions of primaries, scaled by rachis width. All clades are plotted.

9. Middle region: rachis length or barb angle asymmetry vs. body mass

To further examine the potential for size to confound our results, we compared 1) the correlation between rachis length at the middle region (i.e., a measure of feather size) and taxon body mass to 2) the correlation between barb angle asymmetry at the middle region, quantified as $\log_{10}(\text{trailing barb angle})$ divided by $\log_{10}(\text{trailing barb angle})$, and taxon body mass. After applying a linear regression to the \log_{10} -transformed data, we see that feather asymmetry has a far weaker correlation to body mass (Slope = ~ -0.04 , Multiple $R^2 = \sim 0.03$, Adjusted $R^2 = \sim 0.02$) than does feather size (Slope = ~ 0.1 , Multiple $R^2 = \sim 0.06$, Adjusted $R^2 = \sim 0.05$), even with near identical sample sizes (barbless cassowary was dropped from the feather asymmetry regression). Thus, our conclusion that feather asymmetry increases after flight loss is not solely due to confound with body size (i.e., because flightless taxa are larger than their volant relatives).

Body Mass vs. Rachis Length (Middle Region)

Figure S108. Log₁₀-transformed feather size versus body size in our dataset. From the middle region of the feather. Multiple R² = 0.05799, Adjusted R² = 0.04636. Slope = 0.09895. N = 83 taxa.

Body Mass vs. Barb Angle Asymmetry (Middle Region)

Figure S109. Log₁₀-transformed feather asymmetry versus body size in our dataset. From the middle region of the feather. Multiple R² = 0.03484, Adjusted R² = 0.02277. Slope = -0.04003. N = 82 taxa.

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